

ISic3547

I.Sicily inscription 3547

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Museo Pepoli (Trapani) ms. 33 and 221

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337211

1. θεοῖς ἀγν[ο]ῖς

2. πολιοῦχοις

3. ὁ δᾶμος ΚΑΤΙΦΗΣ

4. Δρεπαν [αἰων(?)]

5. εὐεργεσί[α]ς ἔνεκεν.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645622

EDCS 71000783

PHI 337211

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0892

Filippi, A. 2002. Trapani: testimonianze storiche ed archeologiche. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 35: 73-87. At 73 no.8/2

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3547. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388742>